

NIGERIA DIVERSIFICATION AGENDA AND ECONOMIC GROWTH: THE ROLE OF AGRICULTURE

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Abstract

The paper examined the role of agriculture in promoting the diversification agenda and economic growth in Nigeria. The study employed annual time series data obtained from Central Bank of Nigeria statistical bulletin and World Bank Data base for the period 1986 to 2018. The study employed the Phillip-Peron unit root test, ARDL Bounds test for cointegration, and the error correction mechanism. The result of the unit root test revealed that the variables were stationary at mixed order of integration (levels and first difference), while the ARDL Bounds test revealed the presence of a long-run relationship. Findings of the study further revealed that all the components of agricultural production – crop production, livestock production, forestry, and fisheries – exerted a positive and significant long-run effect on economic growth, with livestock production exerting the greatest effect within the study period. The error correction mechanism indicated that 71.07% of the short-run disequilibrium is corrected in the long-run. The paper recommended that for the country to strongly diversify, government needs to invest aggressively on the agricultural sector so as to reap its full potentials.

Keywords: Economic Growth, Lewis Model, Agriculture, ARDL, ECM, Diversification

Introduction

One of the key goals of macroeconomic policies of government is the actualization of economic growth and development. Scholars argue that the Agricultural sector is critical to the attainment of this core macroeconomic goal as espoused in the literature on the subject matter. Agriculture is often regarded as a key driver of

economic growth and development. It was regarded as the mainstay of the Nigerian economy especially in the 1960s and early 1970s before the discovery of crude oil in the country. The performance of an economy especially in terms of growth in per capita income is dependent, among other things, on a well-developed agricultural sector (Olabanji, Adebisi, Ese, and Emmanuel, 2017). This is because the agricultural sector exerts spill over effects on other sectors of the economy and is considered the highest employer of labour in developing countries such as Nigeria. Specifically, the sector employed about two-thirds of the working population with a significant contribution to gross domestic product, and provides a larger proportion of non-oil earnings (CIA, 2013). These spill over effects include inter-sectoral linkages which could be either market-based (direct) or non-market based (indirect). The market-based arguments are of the opinion that the various sectors are linked through the supply of surplus labour to firms in the industrial sector; supply of food for domestic consumption; provision of market for industrial output; supply of domestic savings for industrial investment; and supply of foreign exchange from agricultural export earnings to finance import of intermediate and capital goods (Johnston and Mellor, 1961). The non-market based arguments on the role of agriculture in promoting economic growth arise from governmental learning by doing, increased economic stability, food security, and the relative efficiency of rural household decision-making (Block and Timmer, 1994). Moreover, agriculture indirectly contributes to economic growth through its provision of better caloric nutrient intake by the poor, food availability, food price stability, and poverty reduction (Timmer, 1995).

Despite the many advantages of agriculture, there has been series of fluctuations in the contribution of the sector to national income (GDP). In 1986, the sector contributed about 19.60%, which declined to 17.95% in 1990. The share of agriculture rose to 26.38% as at 2003 with a further increase to 25.56% as at 2006. In 2018, agriculture contributed 25.13% to GDP (Central bank of Nigeria, 2018). Comparing these figures to those of the 1960s where agriculture was a major source of export earnings, it becomes evident that the contribution of agriculture to economic growth in Nigeria has been declining. In the 1960s and 1970s the agricultural sector contributed on the average over 65% of total export, with attendant emphasis on export of cash crops such as cocoa, rubber, hides and skin, groundnut, and palm oil (Kamil, Sevin, and Festus, 2017).

In response to Nigeria quest for agricultural development and diversification of the economy, several schemes and programmes had been formulated and implemented. Such as Agricultural Credit Guarantee Scheme Fund (ACGSF), Agricultural Credit Support Scheme, Commercial Agriculture Credit Scheme, Nigeria Agricultural and Cooperative Bank (now Nigerian Agricultural Cooperative and Rural Development Bank), River Basin Authorities, Agricultural Development Project, and Operation Feed the Nation. These schemes recorded both successes and failures. For instance, the ACGSF value of loans guaranteed as at 1986 stood at N68,417.40, increased to N361,449.00 in 2000, and then to a high record of N7,840,496.63 in 2010. In 2015,

the value of loan was N10,857,380.83 and declined drastically to N5,849,388.73 and N4,377,626.29 in 2017 and 2018 (all values in millions) respectively (CBN, 2018). The major problem of this scheme was the increasing incidence of loan defaults which was attributed to factors such as natural disasters; poor farm management, low product prices, and loan diversion (Njoku, 1986; Ojo, 1986; and Nwosu, 2010).

Nigeria is now at a point where the diversification of the economy seems to be the only panacea to its many economic predicaments. This is especially so in the face of dwindling reserves as a result of falling crude oil prices and mounting debt profile. Currently, the coronavirus (covid-19) pandemic have caused global economic crisis with adverse effects on the African economies including Nigeria. Every economy seems to be locked down in the battle against the virus. The mounting uncertainties in the crude oil market with threats of development in alternative energy such as solar and electricity driven vehicles, and the death-dealing pandemic, indicate gloomy future of oil revenue. Nigeria dependency on oil revenue makes the nation vulnerable in the face of serious threats to its economic growth and development agenda if (of which is likely to be) the demand for oil diminishes which will eventually lead to a fall in oil price. The need for diversification of the economy need not be overemphasized. This information is not new, it is only a restatement of the obvious.

Agriculture is an engine of economic growth and the battle for long-term economic growth will be won or lost in the agricultural sector (Myrdal, 1984). Agricultural development could therefore be regarded as the pathway through which Nigeria can strive towards achieving her diversification agenda and attaining sustainable growth. Sadly, it appears that investments in the agricultural sector are not yielding expected results. This is worrisome. This therefore poses some critical questions such as:

- i. Does agricultural production significantly affect economic growth in Nigeria?
- ii. Which component of agricultural production contributes the greatest to economic growth?
- iii. What is the nature of the long-run relationship (if any) between agricultural production and economic growth in Nigeria?

Based on the research questions stated above, this paper aims at examining the role of agriculture in promoting economic growth in Nigeria, especially now that diversification is a burning issue. Specifically, the paper aims at examining:

- i. the effects of the various components of agriculture on economic growth,
- ii. the component of agricultural production with the greatest contribution to economic growth in Nigeria, and
- iii. the existence of a long-run relationship (if any) between agriculture and economic growth in Nigeria.

The paper is divided into five sections: The introduction, literature review, research methodology, empirical findings, conclusion and recommendations.

Review of Related Literature

Theoretical Literature

The underutilization of the potentials of the Nigerian agricultural sector necessitates the adoption of the Structural-Change Models of economic growth as the theoretical framework for this study. The Structural-Change Theory opines that an economy's "underdevelopment is due to underutilization of resources arising from structural or institutional factors that have their origin in both domestic and international dualisms, hence, development requires more than just accelerated capital formation" (Torado and Smith, 2011). Two of such theories are the Two-Sector Surplus Labour theoretical model propounded by Nobel laureate W. Arthur Lewis in the 1950s which was later modified, formalized and extended by John Fei and Gustav Ranis (see Lewis, 1954 and Fei and Ranis, 1964), and the Patterns of Development by Hollis B. Chenery and his co-authors. The Lewis theory is adopted for this work.

According to the Lewis Model, the underdeveloped economy is made up of two sectors: a traditional, overpopulated rural subsistence sector characterized by zero marginal productivity of labour – a situation that permits Lewis to classify this as surplus labour in the sense that it can be withdrawn from the traditional agricultural sector without any loss of output – and a high-productivity modern urban industrial sector into which labour from the subsistence sector is gradually transferred (Torado and Smith, 2011). This modern sector could also be regarded as "modern agriculture" but, for the purpose of simplicity, it is regarded as "industrial" sector. Following this, the growth model can simply be put as:

$$Y = f(\text{AGR}, \text{INDS}) \quad (1)$$

Where Y is economic development, AGR is the traditional agricultural sector, and INDS is the modern industrial sector. Equation 1 depicts economic dualism and it is assumed, (of which is true), that these two sectors are interrelated. The agricultural sector employs capital, labour, expertise and is also a final consumer of the output of the industrial sector, while the industrial sector employs labour and inputs of the agricultural sector (Inusa *et al.*, 2018). It is also believed that both labour transfers from the traditional sector to the modern industrial sector and subsequent modern-sector employment growth are brought about by output expansion in the modern sector. The rate of industrial investment and capital accumulation are the catalyst for such output expansion.

In summary, Lewis Two-Sector Model is a theory of development in which surplus labour from the traditional agricultural sector is transferred to the modern industrial sector, the growth of which absorbs the surplus labour, promotes industrialization, and stimulate sustained development (Torado and Smith, 2011). The theory focuses on how an underdeveloped country can transform their economy from a traditional subsistence agriculture to a modern one through heavy financial support (industrial investment and capital accumulation) in order to attain industrial breakthrough. Such structural changes that can promote productivity are bank loans, farm inputs distribution, public credit agencies, mechanization of agriculture, irrigation practices, and other modern methods towards agricultural development. Such

practices will boost agricultural production, promotes industrialization hence, economic growth.

The Lewis theory was used in studying the recent growth experience in China and labour markets in other developing countries (Islam and Yokota, 2008; Zhang, Yang, and Wang, 2010; Fang, 2007; Yiping and Tingsong, 2010; and Fields, 2004).

Empirical Literature

The empirical studies on the role of agriculture on economic growth have received attention from many scholars. In their work, Mathew and Adeboye (2010) examined the role of the agricultural sector in economic development of Nigeria. Time series data from 1970 to 2008 were used and the study employed the Johansen co-integration techniques of regression. The result shows that there is no significant impact of agricultural sector on economic development in Nigeria.

Oje-Okoro (2011) carried out an analysis of the contributions of agricultural sector on the Nigeria economic development for the period 1986 to 2007. The multiple regression technique was used to analyse the data collected and the result indicated a positive relationship between Gross Domestic Product (GDP) vis-à-vis domestic savings, government expenditure on agriculture, and Foreign Direct Investment (FDI).

Aminu and Anono (2012) empirically investigated the contribution of agricultural sector and petroleum sector to the economic growth and development (GDP) of the Nigerian economy between 1960 and 2010. The Augmented Dickey-Fuller technique was utilized in testing the unit root property of the series; after which Chow breakpoint test was conducted to test the presence of structural break in the economy. The results of the Augmented Dickey-Fuller unit root test showed that all the variables in the model were stationary at first difference and the results of Chow breakpoint test indicated that there is no structural break in the period under review. Further, the results also revealed that agricultural sector contributed higher than the petroleum sector, though they both possessed a positive impact on the economic growth and development of the economy.

Also, Odetola and Etumnu (2013) investigated the contribution of the agriculture sector to the economic growth of Nigeria for the period 1960 to 2011 using the growth accounting framework and Granger Causality test. The study found that the agricultural sector has contributed positively to the economic growth in Nigeria. The Granger Causality test showed that agricultural growth Granger-causes GDP growth, and not the other way round.

Oyinbo and Rekwot (2014) examined the relationship between agricultural production and the growth of Nigerian economy with focus on poverty reduction. The study employed unit root tests and the bounds (ARDL) testing approach to cointegration. Their findings revealed that agricultural production was significant in

influencing the favourable trend of economic growth in Nigeria. However, there is still high poverty and the study identified the need for a shift from monolithic oil-based economy to a more plural one with agriculture being the lead sector.

In their research work, Ideba, Iniobong, Otu and Itoro (2014) investigated the relationship between agricultural public capital expenditure and economic growth in Nigeria over the period 1961 to 2010. The study employed Augmented Dickey-Fuller test, Johansen maximum likelihood test and Granger Causality test. Result from the cointegration test revealed the existence of a long-run relationship. The Error Correction Model result indicated that public expenditure on agriculture had a positive effect on economic growth while the Granger Causality Test revealed the existence of a unidirectional causality flowing from public expenditure on agriculture to economic growth. The study recommended policy adjustment as a factor needed to promote economic growth.

Abula and Ben (2017) researched on the impact of agricultural output on economic development in Nigeria within the period of 1986 to 2014. Augmented Dickey-Fuller unit root test and Vector Autoregressive Model were adopted as test statistics techniques. The result revealed that agriculture played an important role on Nigeria economic development.

Similarly, the study of Kamil, Seving, and Festus (2017) was an attempt to examine the contributions of agricultural sector on economic growth of Nigeria, using time series data from 1981 to 2013. The findings of the study revealed that there was a positive long run equilibrium relationship between agricultural input and economic growth in Nigeria; although the Vector Error Correction Model result showed that the speed of adjustment of the variables towards their long-run equilibrium path was low.

Inusa, Daniel, Dayagal, and Chiya (2018) attempted an empirical examination of the role of agriculture on Nigerian economic growth and recovery. The study employed the unit root and cointegration techniques. The result from the unit root revealed a mixed order of integration – level and first difference and the cointegration result presented an evidence of a long-run relationship. Result from the Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) regression technique revealed that exchange rate positively and significantly impacted agricultural output. Loans and advances, and total savings were also discovered to have significant impact on agricultural output as a component of GDP.

More recently, Kenny (2019) investigated the role of agricultural sector performance on economic growth in Nigeria using the Vector Error Correction Mechanism (VECM). The major findings revealed a significant long-run relationship between agricultural domestic production and its explanatory variables (Agricultural Credit Guarantee Scheme Fund, Federal Government current expenditure on agriculture, total employment and effect of trade liberalisation), with a 35% speed of adjustment.

LSPR = Livestock production
FRTY = Forestry
FSPR = Fishery production

In its estimable and transformed form, equation 3.3 becomes

$$\log \text{RGDP} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \log \text{CRPR} + \beta_2 \log \text{LSPR} + \beta_3 \log \text{FRTY} + \beta_4 \log \text{FSPR} + \beta_5 \text{INTR} + \beta_6 \text{INFR} + \beta_7 \text{EXCR} + \beta_8 \log \text{GFCF} + \beta_9 \log \text{GEXP} + \mu \quad (3.44)$$

Where log is the natural log, $\beta_0 - \beta_9$ are the parameters to be estimated, and μ is the random error term. Note that INTR, INFR, and EXCR are not in their log form since they are rates. The essence of the log is to help us in linearizing the variables and in explaining the coefficients of the explanatory variables in elasticities.

A priori Expectation

The a priori expectation of the parameters in the model is presented in Table 1.

Table 1: A priori expectation of the coefficients

Variable	Coefficient	A priori expectation
logCRPR	β_1	Positive (+)
logLSPR	β_2	Positive (+)
logFRTy	β_3	Positive (+)
logFSPR	β_4	Positive (+)
INTR	β_5	Negative (-)
INFR	β_6	Positive (+)
EXCR	β_7	Negative (-)
logGFCF	β_8	Positive (+)
logGEXP	β_9	Positive (+)

Data Sources

Data for this study were obtained from Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) statistical bulletin and World Bank data base on World Development Indicators. Specifically, data on RGDP, Agricultural Output (CRPR, LSPR, FRTY, and FSPR), INTR, EXCR, and GEXP were obtained from the 2018 CBN statistical bulletin while data on INFR and GFCF were obtained from the 2018 World Development Indicators.

Analytical Technique

The analytical approach for this paper begins with the diagnostic test, cointegration test, and the Vector Error Correction Mechanism (ECM). The unit root diagnostic test was conducted using the Phillip-Peron test technique developed by Phillip and Perron (1988). Also, the cointegration test helps in detecting the existence of a long-run relationship. This was done using the ARDL Bounds test approach. The VECM helps in detecting how the short-run disequilibrium is corrected in the long-run, i.e. the speed of adjustment. It is represented as the one-period lag of the error term. The use of the ARDL approach is utilized as it easily estimates both the short-run and

long-run estimates. Also, the approach can be utilized irrespective of the order in which the variables are integrated.

Empirical Findings

Unit Root Test

The Phillip-Peron (PP) unit root test result is presented in Table 3.

Table 2: Unit Root Test Result

Variable	PP Statistic	Bandwidth	Test Critical Value (5%)	Decision
Level				
logRGDP	-0.0824	3	-2.9571	Non-stationary
logCRPR	-0.2246	1	-2.9571	Non-stationary
logLSPR	0.8331	3	-2.9571	Non-stationary
logFRTY	1.0030	0	-2.9571	Non-stationary
logFSPR	-0.9638	4	-2.9571	Non-stationary
INTR	-4.7388	4	-2.9571	Stationary
INFR	-2.7751	2	-2.9571	Non-stationary
EXCR	1.0579	2	-2.9571	Non-stationary
logGFCF	-4.8658	0	-2.9571	Stationary
logGEXP	-4.3472	3	-2.9571	Stationary
First Difference				
Δ ogRGDP	-3.1144	0	-2.9604	Stationary
Δ ogCRPR	-5.5238	0	-2.9604	Stationary
Δ ogLSPR	-3.7387	1	-2.9604	Stationary
Δ ogFRTY	-5.539	2	-2.9604	Stationary
Δ ogFSPR	-4.5575	1	-2.9604	Stationary
Δ INFR	-6.7218	19	-2.9604	Stationary
Δ EXCR	-3.9316	3	-2.9604	Stationary

Source: Researcher computation using Eviews 10

The unit root test result presented in Table 2 indicates that the variables are in mixed order of integration – at level and at first difference and Δ is the difference operator. The variables are integrated of a particular order if the PP statistic is more negative than the 5% critical value. From Table, it is evident that INTR, logGFCF, and logGEXP are stationary at level or order zero. On the other hand, logRGDP, logCRPR, logLSPR, logFRTY, logFSPR, INFR, and EXCR are all integrated at first difference or order one. This mixed order of integration necessitated the use of the ARDL Bounds test for cointegration.

ARDL Bounds Test for Cointegration

The ARDL Bounds test for long-run (levels) relationship is presented in Table 4.

Table 3: Bounds Test Result

Critical Value	Lower Bound Value	Upper Bound Value
5%	2.04	2.08
2.5%	2.24	3.35
1%	2.5	3.68

Computed F-statistic = 4.7980 k = 9

Source: Researcher computation using Eviews 10

Based on the result of the Bounds test the null hypothesis of no levels relationship is rejected. This is because the 1%, 2.5%, and 5% critical values both at the lower Bound and in the upper Bound are less than the F-statistic. Hence, we conclude that there is a long-run relationship among the variables. This necessitates the estimation of both the short-run and long-run relationships.

Static (Long-run) Estimates

The long-run estimates is presented in Table 2.

Table 4: Long-run Parameters Estimates

Dependent variable: logRGDP				
Variable	Coefficient	Standard Error	t-statistic	Probability
Constant	2.1592	0.4550	4.7459	0.0001***
<i>logCRPR</i>	0.3118	0.0528	5.9079	0.0000***
<i>logLSPR</i>	0.4936	0.2177	2.2676	0.0331**
<i>logFRTY</i>	0.3008	0.1541	1.9524	0.0632*
<i>logFSPR</i>	0.1546	0.0526	2.9404	0.0073**
<i>INTR</i>	-0.0018	0.0023	-0.7619	0.4539
<i>INFR</i>	0.0007	0.0004	1.6780	0.1069
<i>EXCR</i>	-0.0007	0.0002	-4.0201	0.0005***
<i>logGFCF</i>	0.0056	0.0155	0.35878	0.7230
<i>logGEXP</i>	0.0147	0.0113	1.3012	0.2061
R-squared = 0.9976 Adjusted R-squared = 0.9967 Durbin Watson = 1.85				
F-statistic = 1070.263 Probability of F-statistic = 0.0000***				

Source: Researcher Computation using Eviews 10

The result of the long-run relationship, as depicted in Table 4, reveals an interesting role of the agricultural sector in promoting economic growth. All the components are positively and significantly affecting economic growth in the long-run. This means

that a unit increase in crop production will lead to a 31.18 units increase in economic growth; a unit increase in livestock production will lead to a 49.36 units increase in economic growth; a unit increase in forestry production will lead to a 30.08 units increase in economic growth; while a unit increase in fishery production will lead to a 15.46 units increase in economic growth. The contributions of the individual components of the agricultural sector reveals that investing in the sector is critical to sustaining economic growth in the long-run.

Interest rate and exchange rate, in the long-run, exert negative effect on economic growth, though only exchange rate is significant at 1% level. The implication is that a unit increase in exchange rate will lead to a 0.07 units decrease in economic growth. Inflation rate, gross fixed capital formation, and government expenditure exert positive and insignificant effect on economic growth in the long-run.

The R-squared (0.9976) indicate that 99.76 of the total variation in the dependent variable is explained by the variation in the explanatory variables while the other 0.24% is explained by other variables not captured in the model. This represents a high goodness of fit. The goodness of fit remains quite high (99.67%) after being adjusted for the degree of freedom. The F-statistic is statistically significant at 1% level and this indicate that the overall model is significant. The Durbin Watson statistic (1.85) is approximately 2.0 and this is a clear indication of an absence of serial correlation. Also, since the DW statistic is greater than the R-squared, the result is not spurious.

Estimated Short-run Relationship

The result of the short-run coefficients that is associated with the long-run relationship which is obtained from the error correction mechanism is presented in Table 5.

Table 5: ARDL Short-run Error Correction Estimates

Dependent variable: logRGDP				
Variable	Coefficient	Standard Error	t-statistic	Probability
$\Delta \log CRPR$	0.1796	0.0104	17.3366	0.0004***
$\Delta \log LSPR$	0.3829	0.0434	8.8313	0.0031**
$\Delta \log FRTY$	-0.2465	0.0465	-5.2973	0.0131**
$\Delta \log FSPR$	-0.2060	0.0228	-9.0496	0.0028**
$\Delta INTR$	-0.0040	0.0006	-6.9888	0.0060**
$\Delta INFR$	-0.0025	0.0002	-11.1748	0.0015**
$\Delta EXCR$	-0.0006	4.74E-05	-12.8631	0.0010**
$\Delta \log GFCF$	0.0196	0.0017	11.2465	0.0015**
$\Delta \log GEXP$	-0.1186	0.0085	-13.9721	0.0008***
$ECM(-1)$	-0.7107	0.0470	-15.1230	0.0006***
R-squared = 0.9950		Adjusted R-squared = 0.9884		Durbin Watson = 2.13

Source: Researcher Computation using Eviews 10

The coefficient of the error term (-0.7107) is rightly signed and statistically significant at the 1% level of significant. Also, the speed of adjustment is quite high. The coefficient implies that 71.07% of the short-run disequilibrium in the previous year is corrected in the long-run. All the components of the agricultural output and other variables in the model are observed to have a short-run significant effect on economic growth. However, in the short-run analysis, forestry and fishery components of agricultural production have a negative effect on economic growth while crop production and livestock production exerted a positive effect on economic growth. Also, interest rate, inflation rate, exchange rate, and government expenditure has a negative effect on economic growth in the short-run while gross fixed capital formation has a positive effect on economic growth. Some of these coefficients deviates from the long-run estimates. Whereas all the coefficient of agricultural output components are positive in the long-run; inflation is positive in the long-run but negative in the short-run; government expenditure is also positive in the long-run but negative in the short-run. The reasons for this could be the time lag for yields on government spending to be actualized. Also, the misappropriation of public funds meant for investment in agriculture could, at least, in the short-run affect national output. The persistent insecurity crisis and the constant farmer-herders crisis in the country have severely cripple agricultural activities. However, continuous investment in the sector and adamant adherence to the target of revamping and modernizing the sector promote production, productivity will increase, resulting in higher prices for inputs; and the high prices will greatly enhance supply in the long-run for profit making firms in the face of inelastic demand for agricultural product.

Discussion of Findings

The agricultural sector is a propeller of economic growth both in the long-run and in the short-run. In the long-run, all the four components of agricultural production – crop production, livestock production, forestry, and fishery – are all positive and statistically significant. This is a clear indication that investment in agriculture can set the trajectory for the country's economy to a path of sustainable growth. This is so because investment in agriculture results in spill over effects on other sectors of the economy, especially the industrial sector. It further portrays the fact that agricultural sector can be potent in driving sustainable economic growth if serious investment is channelled to the sector as the drive towards diversification in the country is a necessity. Livestock production is seen to exert a greater effect on economic growth followed by crop production, forestry and fishery. The low contribution of fishery is attributed to the gross negligence to aquaculture and heavy investment in feeds in the sub-sector.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The agricultural sector is a critical sector that will promote sustainable economic growth in the country and therefore a crucial sector for the diversification agenda. At a time such as this where the global outlook is bleak due to the corona virus pandemic and falling crude oil prices, a departure from over dependence on oil to a diversified economy with a strong and vibrant agricultural sector is the panacea to maintaining

long-term survival and economic resilience. Only then can the Nigeria economy withstand the ugly shocks due to uncertainties in global oil prices and a sudden pandemic. The lacklustre approach towards diversification is to be avoided as plague. This is necessary because Nigeria seems to be reactive instead of proactive in the face of a looming catastrophe. The paper attempt to examine the role of agricultural sector in economic growth of the country with a view to projecting investment in the sector as part of the diversification agenda. The paper revealed that all the components of the agricultural production are growth promoting and exert significant effects. Further, the paper revealed that livestock production contributes mostly to the economic growth of the country while fishery contributed the least. The Bounds test for levels relationship indicated the presence of a long-run relationship between economic growth and the explanatory variables in the model, while the ECM indicated that 71.07% of the short-run disequilibrium is corrected in the long-run.

In line with the findings, the paper recommended that for the country to strongly diversify, government needs to invest aggressively on the agricultural sector so as to reap its full potentials. Concerted efforts should be geared towards promoting livestock production as well as subsidizing fishery so as to unveil the potentials inherent in the component.

There is also the need to develop and strengthen agriculture value chain so as to promote a positive spill over effect on other sectors (e.g the manufacturing sector) and reduce wastages.

There is need to strengthen and ensure exchange rate stability since it is observed that it exert a negative and significant effect on growth. Linking this to the agricultural sector, most of the inputs are imported and a high exchange rate will be detrimental to the growth of the sector and the economy as a whole.

Finally, there is need to fight corruption to the fullest as this is a canker worm that can devour the potentials that the country can reap from the agricultural sector. There is need for proper management and monitoring of funds allocated to the sector, as well as monitoring and supervising policies that are geared towards improving agricultural production in Nigeria.

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